

Analysis of the Monitoring and Evaluation Report (2022) of the Municipal Education Plan of São José dos Campos

Análise do Relatório de Monitoramento e Avaliação (2022) do Plano Municipal de Educação de São José dos Campos
Análisis del Informe de Monitoreo y Evaluación (2022) del Plan Municipal de Educación de São José dos Campos

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Abstract:

As an element of public educational policy, the Municipal Education Plan (PME) is a strategic tool developed by municipalities, aimed at local educational development. Developed based on national guidelines and adjusted to the specific needs of each municipality, the PME, through the definition of local guidelines, strategies and goals, seeks to meet varied educational demands. In this sense, the article presents an analysis of the Monitoring and Evaluation Report of the Municipal Education Plan of São José dos Campos, to verify the fulfillment of its twenty goals, in the year 2022, and understand the advances and challenges faced. The option for an exploratory approach methodology, with a quantitative focus and based on bibliographic and documentary design, made it possible to infer that there were very significant improvements, such as in the item of expansion of early childhood education places, at the same time that difficulties were highlighted, such as the achievement of goals related to the continued training of teachers and the appreciation of teaching.

Keywords: *Education; Educational Management; Educational Planning; Municipal Education Plan.*

Resumo:

Como elemento de política pública educacional, o Plano Municipal de Educação (PME) é uma ferramenta estratégica elaborada pelos municípios, que visa ao desenvolvimento educacional local. Desenvolvido a partir de diretrizes nacionais e ajustado às necessidades específicas de cada município, o PME, por meio da definição de diretrizes, estratégias e metas locais, busca atender a demandas educacionais variadas. Nesse sentido, o artigo apresenta uma análise do Relatório de Monitoramento e Avaliação do Plano Municipal de Educação de São José dos Campos, a fim de verificar o cumprimento de suas 20 metas, no ano de 2022, e compreender os avanços e os desafios enfrentados. A opção por uma metodologia de abordagem exploratória, com foco quantitativo e baseada no delineamento bibliográfico e documental, possibilitou inferir que houve melhorias muito significativas, como no item de ampliação das vagas de educação infantil, ao mesmo tempo em que se apontaram dificuldades, como o alcance de metas relacionadas à formação continuada de professores e à valorização do magistério.

Palavras-chave: *Educação; Gestão Educacional; Planejamento Educacional; Plano Municipal de Educação.*

Resumen:

Como elemento de la política pública educativa, el Plan Municipal de Educación (PME) es una herramienta estratégica desarrollada por los municipios, orientada al desarrollo educativo local. Desarrollado con base en lineamientos nacionales y ajustado a las necesidades específicas de cada municipio, el PME, a través de la definición de lineamientos, estrategias y metas locales, busca atender variadas demandas educativas. En este sentido, el artículo presenta un análisis del Informe de Monitoreo y Evaluación del Plan Municipal de Educación de São José dos Campos, con el fin de verificar el cumplimiento de sus 20 metas, en el año 2022, y comprender los avances y desafíos enfrentados. La opción por una metodología de enfoque exploratorio, con enfoque cuantitativo y basada en un diseño bibliográfico y documental, permitió inferir que hubo mejoras muy significativas, como en el rubro de ampliación de plazas de educación infantil, al mismo tiempo que se destacaron dificultades, como el logro de metas relacionadas con la formación continua de los docentes y la valorización de la enseñanza.

Palabras clave: *Educación; Gestión Educativa; Planificación Educativa; Plan Municipal de Educación.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The municipal education plan is a fundamental piece in the normative framework of an educational system, representing not merely a bureaucratic document, but a robust planning and management tool that can drive innovation in education. By establishing specific guidelines, goals, and strategies for educational development at the local level, the municipal plan offers a unique opportunity to align educational policies with each community's needs and realities. In this sense, the importance of the municipal plan as a contribution to innovation in education lies not only in its capacity to guide the efficient allocation of resources and the management of educational systems, but also in its ability to stimulate significant changes in teaching and learning processes to achieve its goals.

This research aims to analyze the Municipal Education Plan (MEP) Monitoring and Evaluation Report for the municipality of São José dos Campos, covering the period from February 2022 to December 2022. This Monitoring and Evaluation Report serves as a basis for guiding the continuity of the MEP's actions and strategies, considering the progress and needs identified during this period.

As described by Toledo (2016, p. 47), the educational planning process is essentially a sequence of decisions arising from identified demands, taking into account available time and resources. On the other hand, the resulting plan serves as a tangible record of these decisions, ensuring the fulfillment of the commitments made during planning. By avoiding improvisation and promoting well-founded, reflective action, the plan maximizes the efficient use of time and resources. Furthermore, it allows continuous evaluation of progress toward established objectives, enabling adjustments and corrections throughout the school year. Thus, each educational planning process results in a specific plan, whether it be a curriculum plan, a course plan, a subject plan, a lesson plan, or, in the case of the municipality, a Municipal Education Plan (MEP).

2. EDUCATIONAL LEGISLATION AND THE MUNICIPAL EDUCATION PLAN

The 1988 Federal Constitution, in its Article 214, as amended by Constitutional Amendment No. 59/09, states that:

The law will establish the national education plan, with a ten-year duration, to articulate the national education system in a collaborative framework and define guidelines, objectives, goals, and implementation strategies to ensure the maintenance and development of education at its various levels, stages, and modalities through integrated actions of the public authorities of the different federative spheres that lead to:

I - Eradication of illiteracy;

II - Universalization of school attendance;

III - Improving the quality of education;

IV - Training for work;

V - Humanistic, scientific and technological promotion of the country.

VI - Establishing a target for the application of public resources in education as a proportion of the gross domestic product. (Brazil, 1988, our translation)

As a consequence of the current Federal Constitution, Federal Law No. 9,394, of December 20, 1996, the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education (LDBEN - Lei de Diretrizes e Bases da Educação Nacional), also known as "LDB," was created, establishing the guidelines and bases of national education, providing support for educational policies and the establishment of a National Education Plan with the force of law. Article 9, item I, defines that the Union will be responsible for "preparing the National Education Plan, in collaboration with the States, the Federal District, and the Municipalities." Article 11, item I, establishes that the Municipalities will be responsible for "organizing, maintaining, and developing the official bodies and institutions of their education systems, integrating them into the educational policies and plans of the Union and the States" (Brazil, 1996). On January 9, 2001, during the administration of President Fernando Henrique Cardoso, the National Education Plan was approved by Law No. 10,172. According to Bordignon and Paim (2016, p. 24), "[...] many of its fundamental principles did not achieve the proposed objectives, especially regarding investments, teacher training, access to early childhood education, and literacy." Subsequently, the document was improved through Law No. Law 13.005, of June 25, 2014, approved the National Education Plan (PNE – Plano Nacional de Educação), which is currently in effect for a period of 10 years, from 2014 to 2024. Article 8 of this law stipulates that "the States, the Federal District, and the Municipalities must prepare their corresponding education plans, or adapt the plans already approved by law, in accordance with the guidelines, goals, and strategies foreseen in this PNE, within 1 (one) year from the publication of this Law" (Brazil, 2014, our translation). Article 2 of this law established the following guidelines:

- I - Eradication of illiteracy;
- II - Universalization of school attendance;
- III - Overcoming educational inequalities, with an emphasis on promoting citizenship and eradicating all forms of discrimination;
- IV - Improving the quality of education;
- V - Training for work and citizenship, with emphasis on the moral and ethical values on which society is based;
- VI - Promoting the principle of democratic management of public education;
- VII - Humanistic, scientific, cultural and technological promotion of the country;
- VIII - Establishing a target for the application of public resources in education as a proportion of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), ensuring that the needs for expansion are met with quality and equity standards;
- IX - Valuing education professionals;
- X - Promoting the principles of respect for human rights, diversity, and socio-environmental sustainability.

Thus, with the creation of federal educational legislation, all federative entities are responsible for developing their education plans. As stated by Raimann (2020, p. 3, our translation), "with the National Education Plan (2014-2024) approved, the 5,570 Brazilian municipalities were responsible not only for developing their Municipal Education Plans, but also for carrying out actions for the proper implementation of said plans".

3. METHOD

This study adopts an exploratory approach with a bibliographic and documentary design, aiming to deepen the understanding of educational outcomes in the municipality of São José dos Campos. The choice of this methodology is justified by the need to conduct a broad, detailed investigation of the relevant perspectives, theories, and concepts that may relate to the topic under analysis.

As highlighted by Gil (2022, p. 41), exploratory research is beneficial when greater familiarity with a little-known or underexplored subject is desired, enabling the identification of variables and the formulation of more precise hypotheses for subsequent investigations. In this way, the exploratory approach enables a comprehensive analysis of the topic's conceptual landscape, establishing a solid foundation for the study.

A bibliographic and documentary approach was adopted for data collection and analysis, as this study primarily relies on secondary sources, such as books, government reports, and institutional documents. Following Nascimento's definition (2016, p. 27), bibliographic research presupposes consulting a variety of works on the same subject to verify diverse opinions. Documentary research involves analyzing written documents, such as laws, regulations, and statutes. Among the papers used, the Municipal Education Plan (2015-2025) and the Municipal Education Plan Monitoring and Evaluation Report for São José dos Campos stand out. The latter was prepared based on official information from the National Institute of Educational Studies and Research Anísio Teixeira (INEP - Instituto Nacional de Estudos e Pesquisas Educacionais), in addition to the Statistical Synopses of Basic Education and Higher Education of 2022, data from the Seade Foundation, and information considered unofficial, collected by the e-SISTAE data collection system of the Municipal Education Network.

The data analysis consisted of critically reviewing and systematizing the relevant information from the selected sources to deepen existing knowledge on the subject.

It should be noted that, despite being based on secondary sources, this study sought to ensure the reliability and validity of the information through careful selection of sources and the analysis of data from diverse perspectives.

In this way, combining an exploratory approach with bibliographic and documentary research enables a broad, in-depth investigation of the topic, potentially advancing technical and scientific knowledge in education and public policy.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Municipal Education Plan (MEP) of the municipality of São José dos Campos is a document created via municipal law no. 9298 of October 14, 2015, with a validity of ten years, in compliance with the National Education Plan (PNE – Plano Nacional de Educação) and item I of article 11 of Federal Law 9.394, of December 20, 1996 (LDB), which establishes the guidelines and bases of national education.

The MEP of São José dos Campos comprises 20 goals for improving education in the municipality. The table below presents the updated description of these goals:

Table 1 – Goals of the São José dos Campos Municipal Education Plan (2015-2025) – (part 1)

GOALS OF THE MUNICIPAL EDUCATION PLAN OF SÃO JOSÉ DOS CAMPOS (2015-2025)
Goal 1: To guarantee, starting in the 2016 school year, the availability of places for all four- and five-year-old children residing in the Municipality, universalizing preschool; and, by 2020, to meet 100% (one hundred percent) of the active demand for daycare (from zero to three years old).
Goal 2: Consolidate access to nine-year primary education for the entire population aged six to fourteen, ensuring that by the end of 2025 at least 99.5% (ninety-nine point five percent) of students in the Municipal Education Network complete this stage at the recommended age; and, collaboratively, support the strategies that may be established in the State Education Plan for the State Education Network.
Goal 3: To support the strategies established in the State Education Plan for the universalization, by 2016, of school attendance for the population aged fifteen to seventeen.
Goal 4: To universalize, within the scope of the Municipality's responsibilities and in collaboration with the State, access to basic education and specialized educational services for the population aged four to seventeen with disabilities, global developmental disorders, and high abilities or giftedness, preferably within the regular education system, guaranteeing an inclusive educational system by means of multifunctional resource rooms, classes, schools, or specialized services, whether public or contracted.
Goal 5: Ensure all children are literate by the end of the second year of elementary school at the latest. (Already updated according to the amendment made by Law 10.472, of February 25, 2022).
Goal 6: To offer comprehensive education in such a way that the time students spend at school, or under its responsibility, becomes equal to or greater than seven hours per day throughout the school year in at least 50% (fifty percent) of public schools, to serve at least 25% (twenty-five percent) of students in Basic Education.
Goal 7: To promote, within the scope of the Municipality's responsibilities and in collaboration with the State and the Federal Government, the quality of basic education at all stages and modalities, improving school flow and learning, aiming to achieve by 2021 the target established for the Municipality in the Basic Education Development Index – IDEB.
Goal 8: To raise, within the scope of the Municipality's responsibilities and in collaboration with the State, the average schooling of the population aged eighteen to twenty-nine, to reach at least twelve years of study in the last year of validity of the Municipal Education Plan for the rural populations, the region with the lowest schooling in the Municipality and the poorest 25% (twenty-five percent), and to equalize the average education between blacks and non-blacks as declared to the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics Foundation.
Goal 9: Eliminate illiteracy in the Municipality by the end of this Municipal Education Plan and reduce the rate of functional illiteracy by 50% (fifty percent).
Goal 10: To offer at least 25% (twenty-five percent) of enrollments in Youth and Adult Education II in a form integrated with vocational education; and, in Youth and Adult Education at the High School level, to support the initiatives of the State Network foreseen in the State Education Plan, adapting them to the needs of the Municipality.
Goal 11: To support, within the scope of the Municipality's responsibilities and in collaboration with the State and the Federal Government, the strategies foreseen in the National and State Education Plans that aim to triple enrollments in technical vocational education, ensuring the quality of the offer and at least 50% (fifty percent) of the expansion in the public sector.
Goal 12: To support, within the scope of the Municipality's responsibilities and in collaboration with the State and the Union, the increase in enrollment rates in higher education as proposed by the National Education Plans.

Source: SME (*Secretaria Municipal de Educação*, 2015)

Table 1 – Goals of the São José dos Campos Municipal Education Plan (2015-2025) – (part 2)

<p>Goal 13: To support, within the scope of the Municipality's responsibilities and in collaboration with the State and the Federal Government, the improvement of the quality of higher education and the increase in the proportion of masters and doctoral degree holders among the teaching staff actively working in the higher education system as a whole, in accordance with the strategies foreseen in the National and State Education Plans.</p>
<p>Goal 14: To support, within the Municipality, the strategies foreseen in the National and State Education Plans to gradually increase the number of enrollments in "stricto sensu" postgraduate programs, to achieve the annual graduation of sixty thousand master's and twenty-five thousand doctors.</p>
<p>Goal 15: To support, within the scope of the Municipality's responsibilities and in collaboration with the State and the Federal Government, the strategies foreseen in the National and State Education Plans to ensure specific higher education training for all basic education teachers, obtained through a bachelor's degree in the field in which they work.</p>
<p>Goal 16: To support, within the scope of the Municipality's responsibilities, the strategies foreseen in the National and State Education Plans for the postgraduate training of 50% (fifty percent) of Basic Education teachers, until the last year of validity of the National Education Plan, and to guarantee to all Basic Education professionals, continuing education in their area of expertise.</p>
<p>Goal 17: To value the teaching professionals of the Public Basic Education Networks to equalize their average income with that of other professionals with equivalent schooling in the Municipality, by the end of the fifth year of validity of this Municipal Education Plan.</p>
<p>Goal 18: Ensure the improvement of career plans for professionals in Basic Education and Public Higher Education across all education systems; and, for the career plan of professionals in Public Basic Education, take the national professional minimum wage as a reference.</p>
<p>Goal 19: To ensure, within two years, the conditions for the effective implementation of democratic management of education, associated with performance criteria and public consultation with the school community, within the scope of the Municipality's public schools.</p>
<p>Goal 20: To implement actions to increase the municipal education budget and public investment in public education to contribute to achieving the targets in proportion to the Gross Domestic Product foreseen in the National, State and this Municipal Education Plan.</p>

Source: SME (Secretaria Municipal de Educação, 2015)

The Monitoring and Evaluation Report of the Municipal Education Plan (MEP) presents the performance of the goals and strategies during the analyzed period. This research examined the 2022 results and observed, in the Municipal Education Plan Monitoring and Evaluation Report for São José dos Campos, that Goal 1 of the MEP, which refers to Early Childhood Education, shows, in Indicator 1A, the percentage of children aged 4 to 5 years attending school. The target set for 2022 was 100%, while the target achieved during the period (official data) was 94.9%. The number of children aged 4 to 5 years enrolled in preschool in 2022 was 18,480 (INEP, 2023), while the projected school-age population (4 to 5 years) in 2022 was 19,453 (SEADE, 2023). The results indicate that the Municipal Education Network achieved complete coverage of demand for the respective year, ensuring a place for all guardians of children aged 4 and 5 seeking enrollment in its school units. However, it is essential to note that, according to the 2022 population projection, 973 children in this age group were not enrolled due to insufficient demand for early childhood education. Indicator 1B refers to the percentage of children aged 0 to 3 who attend school.

The target set for 2022 was 100%, and the target achieved during the period (official data) was 57%. The number of children aged 0 to 3 years enrolled in daycare centers in 2022 was 20,596 (INEP, 2023), while the projected school-age

population aged 0 to 3 years was 36,110 (SEADE, 2023). Indicator 1C presents the percentage of expressed demand for children aged 4- and 5-year-olds attending school in the Municipal Education Network. The target set for 2022 was 100%, and the target achieved during the period (unofficial data) was also 100%. The list of registered and enrolled children for the year 2022, by age group of 4 and 5 years, in the municipal network, was 15,241. Indicator 1D shows the percentage of expressed demand for children aged 0 to 3 years attending school in the Municipal Education Network. The target set for 2022 was 100%, and the target achieved during the period (unofficial data) was 100%. The list of registered children for the year 2022 by age group from 0 to 3 years in the municipal network was 17,649, and the number of enrollments called in 2022 by age group from 0 to 3 years in the municipal network was also 17,649.

Goal 2 refers to Elementary Education. Indicator 2A shows the percentage of people aged 6 to 14 who have attended or completed elementary education in the municipality. The target set for 2022 was 98.6%, and the target achieved during the period (official data) was 97.2%. In 2022, there were 85,536 enrollments in elementary education, with 83,219 in the 6-14-year-old age group. (INEP, 2023). Indicator 2B concerns the percentage of students who passed or completed elementary education within the municipal network. The target set for 2022 was 99.1%, and the target achieved during the period (unofficial data) was 99.7%. In 2022, the municipal network had 37,835 enrollments in elementary education (INEP, 2023), and 37,738 students passed or completed elementary education (INEP, 2023).

Goal 3 refers to secondary education. Indicator 3A shows the percentage of the population aged 15-17 attending secondary education. The target set for 2022 was 94%, and the target achieved in the period (official data) was 92.9%. The number of enrollments in secondary education in 2022 by age group of 15-17 years was 25,098, while the total number of enrollments in secondary education in 2022 was 27,007 (INEP, 2023).

Goal 4 refers to Special/Inclusive Education. Indicator 4A shows the percentage of 4- to 17-year-olds with disabilities, Global Developmental Disorders (GDD), and high abilities who study in regular basic education classes. No specific number was defined for the 2022 goal, but the goal achieved during the period (official data) was 3.1%. The number of enrollments in basic education in 2022, by age group 4 to 17 years, was 133,739, while the number of enrollments in special education in regular classes in 2022, by age group up to 17 years, was 4,176. (INEP, 2023)

Goal 5 refers to Literacy. Indicator 5A shows the percentage of students who completed the 3rd grade in the alphabetic phase in the Municipal Education Network. The target for 2022 was 100%; however, in accordance with Law No. 10,472 of February 25, 2022, the monitoring of this goal began in the 2022 report onwards via indicator 5B. Indicator 5B shows the percentage of students who completed the 2nd grade in the alphabetic phase in the Municipal Education Network. The target set for 2022 was 100%, while the target achieved in the period (unofficial data) was 85%. The number of enrollments in the 2nd year of the Municipal Education Network in 2022 was 4,436 (INEP, 2023), while the

number of students from the Municipal Network who completed the 2nd year in the alphabetic phase in 2022 was 3,796.

Goal 6 refers to Comprehensive Education. Indicator 6A shows the percentage of public schools offering full-time education. The target set for 2022 was 41%, while the target achieved during the period (official data) was 37.5%. In 2022, the municipality had 197 public basic education establishments (INEP, 2023), while 74 offered full-time education (INEP, 2023). Indicator 6B concerns the percentage of students enrolled in public schools on a full-time basis. The target for 2022 was 18%, and the target achieved during the period (according to official data) was 13.4%. The number of enrollments in basic education in public schools in 2022 was 114,062, while the number of enrollments in full-time public schools in 2022 was 15,282 (INEP, 2023). Indicator 6C shows the percentage of schools in the direct and partner municipal network offering full-time education. The target set for 2022 was 41%, and the target achieved during the period (unofficial data) was 57.7%. There were 163 schools in the direct and partner municipal networks, of which 94 offered full-time education. Indicator 6D shows the percentage of students enrolled in the municipal network aged 0 to 17 years in full-time education. The target set for 2022 was 18%, and the target achieved during the period (unofficial data) was 20.3%. The number of enrollments in the municipal network in the 0 to 17 age group was 71,530, of which 14,506 were in the municipal network offering full-time education.

Goal 7 refers to Appropriate Learning at the Right Age. It was observed that the Municipal Government's report did not provide information on this goal for the year 2022, only for 2021. Indicator 7A presents the municipality's average IDEB score for the initial years of elementary school, every two years. The target set for 2021 was 6.9, and the target achieved in the period (official data) was 6.7 (INEP, 2022). Indicator 7B presents the municipality's average IDEB score for the final years of elementary school. The target set for 2021 was 6.4, while the target achieved in the period (official data) was 5.6 (INEP, 2022). Indicator 7C shows the municipality's average IDEB score for high school. The target for 2021 was 4.4, and the target achieved during that period (according to official data) was also 4.4 (INEP, 2022).

Goal 8 refers to Average Schooling. Indicator 8A shows the percentage of enrollments in the EJA (Youth and Adult Education) program among the population aged 18 to 29. There was no defined goal for 2022, but the goal achieved in the period (official data) was 1.4%. The number of enrollments in the EJA program in 2022 for the 18 to 29-year-old age group was 1,812 (INEP, 2023), while the estimated population in 2022 for the same age group was 125,313 (SEADE, 2023).

Goal 9 concerns Literacy and Functional Literacy among Young People and Adults. Indicator 9A presents the illiteracy rate of the population aged 15 years or older. The target set for 2022 was 1.5%, and the target achieved in the period (official data) was 3%. (SEADE, 2023)

Goal 10 refers to Youth and Adult Education (EJA) integrated with Vocational Education. Indicator 10A shows the percentage of EJA enrollments in integrated

vocational education. The target set for 2022 was 10%, while the target achieved in the period (official data) was 0% (INEP, 2023). Indicator 10B presents the percentage of actions taken to increase the number of EJA enrollments in public vocational education. The target set for 2022 was 70%, while the target achieved in the period (unofficial data) was 88.8%.

Goal 11 refers to Vocational Education. Indicator 11A presents the absolute number of enrollments in public and private Vocational and Technological Education (VTE). The target set for 2022 was 20,626, while the target achieved during the period (official data) was 7,632. The number of enrollments in 2022 for secondary education and vocational education at the secondary level was 27,007, while the number of enrollments in vocational education at the secondary level in 2022 was 7,632 (INEP, 2023). Indicator 11B shows the number of enrollments in VTE in the public sector. The target set for 2022 was 3,368. The target achieved during the period (official data) was 2,773. In 2022, the number of enrollments in vocational education at the secondary level was 7,179, while the number in the public network was 2,773 (INEP, 2023).

Goal 12 refers to Higher Education. Indicator 12A presents the gross enrollment rate in undergraduate programs in the municipality. There was no defined target for 2022, but the target achieved during the period (according to official data) was 7.2%. The number of undergraduate enrollments in 2022 was 38,482 (INEP, 2023), while the projected population in the five-year age group aged 20 in 2022 was 532,573 (SEADE, 2023). Indicator 12B shows the percentage of actions taken to increase undergraduate enrollment in the municipality. The target set for 2022 was 70%, while the target achieved during the period (unofficial data) was 93.7%.

Goal 13 refers to the Qualification of Higher Education Professors. Indicator 13A shows the percentage of actions taken to increase the number of master's and doctoral degree holders in higher education. The target set for 2022 was 70%. The target achieved during the period (unofficial data) was 85.7%. Indicator 13B shows the percentage of master's- and doctoral-degree holders among higher education teaching staff. This goal was not evaluated in 2022, but in 2021, the target achieved during the period was 86.4%. In 2021, 940 professors were working in higher education, and 813 master's and doctoral degree holders were on the teaching staff (INEP, 2022).

Goal 14 refers to Postgraduate Studies. Indicator 14A addresses the percentage of teachers with master's degrees in basic education. There was no defined goal for 2022, but the goal achieved in the period (official data) was 4.1%. In 2022, there were 7,918 teachers in basic education, of whom 325 held a master's degree (INEP, 2023). Indicator 14B presents the percentage of teachers with doctorates in basic education. No target was set for 2022, but the goal achieved during the period (according to official data) was 0.9%. In 2022, there were 7,918 teachers in basic education, of whom 68 held a doctorate (INEP, 2023). Indicator 14C shows the percentage of actions taken to gradually increase the number of master's and doctoral degree holders. The target set for 2022 was 70%, and the target achieved in the period (unofficial data) was 66.6%.

Goal 15 refers to Teacher Training. Indicator 15A shows the percentage of

teachers with higher education compatible with the area of knowledge in which they teach in basic education. The target set for 2022 was 90%, but the target achieved in the period (official data) was 98.9%. In 2022, there were 7,918 teachers in basic education, of whom 7,833 held a bachelor's degree (INEP, 2023).

Goal 16 refers to Continuing Education and Postgraduate Studies for Teachers. Indicator 16A shows the percentage of teachers in the municipality with postgraduate specialization (*lato sensu*). The target set for 2022 was 42%, while the target achieved in the period (official data) was 32.8%. In 2022, there were 7,918 basic education teachers, of whom 2,598 held postgraduate degrees. (INEP, 2023).

Goal 17 refers to Teacher Appreciation. Indicator 17A shows the difference between a teacher's base salary in the municipal school system and the base salary of other professionals in the same system with equivalent education. The target set for 2022 was R\$ 401.00, while the target achieved during the period (unofficial data) was \geq R\$ 135.36.

Goal 18 refers to the Teacher Career Plan. Indicator 18A shows the difference between a teacher's base salary in the Municipal Education Network and the national minimum wage. No target was set for 2022, but the target achieved during the period (official data) was \geq R\$ 769.12.

Goal 19 refers to Democratic Management. Indicator 19A presents the percentage of unified elections for school councils in the municipality. No target was set for 2022, but the target achieved during the period (unofficial data) was 100%. In 2022, there were 78 state-run schools and 115 municipal schools. (INEP, 2023).

Finally, goal 20 refers to Education Financing. Indicator 20A shows the value of public investment in public education. There was no target set for 2022, but the target achieved in the period (unofficial data), according to the report, was R\$ 823,959,249.68.

5. CONCLUSION

An analysis of the Municipal Education Plan (MPE) of São José dos Campos for 2022 reveals interesting aspects of the municipality's educational landscape. By addressing each of the 20 goals proposed by the MEP, it was possible to identify both significant advances and challenges across different areas of education.

One of the most highlighted aspects of this analysis was the scope of Early Childhood Education, represented by Goal 1 of the Municipal Education Plan (MPE). Although the 2022 goal of reaching 100% of children aged 4 to 5 attending school was not fully achieved, the data reveal considerable effort by the Municipal Education Network to ensure preschool access for most children in this age group. However, the difference between the number of children enrolled and the population projection underscores the need for more effective outreach and community engagement strategies to reach those not yet included in the educational system.

The same pattern of effort and challenge is observed in other goals, such as Goal 2, which concerns Elementary Education, and Goal 6, related to Comprehensive Education. Although progress has been made in enrollment and service, there is still a long way to go to achieve the established goals.

Furthermore, it is essential to highlight the need for greater transparency and information availability for some goals, such as Goal 7, which addresses Appropriate Learning at the Right Age. The absence of 2022 data underscore the need to improve monitoring and evaluation systems to ensure a more comprehensive and accurate assessment of the municipality's educational progress.

Nevertheless, it is concerning to note the existing gaps in goals such as Youth and Adult Education (EJA) integrated with Vocational Education (Goal 10) and Vocational Education (Goal 11). The low achievement of goals in these areas indicates the need to redouble investments and efforts in promoting educational opportunities that meet the demands of the labor market and promote social inclusion.

Regarding Higher Education (Goal 12) and the Qualification of Higher Education Teachers (Goal 13), the data reveal a mixed scenario of progress and challenges. While the gross enrollment rate in undergraduate programs has improved significantly, increasing the number of master's and doctoral degree holders still requires greater emphasis and investment from public policy.

Teacher training and professional development (Goals 14-18) are pillars of quality education. Although there has been progress in initial and ongoing training, salary disparities and unmet goals reveal the need for professional recognition and better working conditions for educators.

Finally, Democratic Management (Goal 19) and Education Financing (Goal 20) emerge as cross-cutting elements that permeate all dimensions of municipal education. Democratic participation and the guarantee of adequate resources are essential for the implementation of educational policies and the achievement of significant results.

In summary, the analysis of the Municipal Education Plan (MEP) of São José dos Campos highlights the complexity and diversity of challenges in the educational context. An integrated, continuous approach to monitoring and evaluation in the MEP can help adjust strategies to overcome these challenges and ensure quality education is accessible to all. The study can offer functional parameters to guide future educational policies and practices, underscoring the importance of continuous investment and commitment to promoting high-quality, innovative education for all citizens.

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